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SUCCESSFUL PERSONAL SELLING AS AN INDICATOR OF PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY EFFECTIVENESS OF AN ARCHITECTURAL AND CONSTRUCTION COMPANY MANAGER IN THE CONTEXT OF MARKETING COMPLEX TRANSFORMATION

УСПІШНИЙ ПЕРСОНАЛЬНИЙ ПРОДАЖ ЯК ПОКАЗНИК ЕФЕКТИВНОСТІ ПРОФЕСІЙНОЇ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ МЕНЕДЖЕРА АРХІТЕКТУРНО-БУДІВЕЛЬНОЇ КОМПАНІЇ В УМОВАХ ТРАНСФОРМАЦІЇ КОМПЛЕКСУ МАРКЕТИНГУ

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Мака́тора Д.А., Кубанов Р.А., Куліков О.П. Успішний персональний продаж як показник ефективності професійної діяльності менеджера архітектурно-будівельної компанії в умовах трансформації комплексу маркетингу. Оглядова стаття.

Метою дослідження є вивчення впливу трансформації комплексу маркетингу на успішність персональних продажів в архітектурно-будівельних компаніях. Предметом аналізу є концепція «4С» (споживач, вартість, зручність, комунікація). Особливу увагу приділено ролі персонального маркетингу та персоналізованого підходу до клієнтів. Це важливі фактори успіху в сучасному бізнес-середовищі. Зроблено висновок, що архітектурно-будівельним менеджерам необхідно постійно вдосконалювати свої навички ефективної комунікації, вміти визначати потреби клієнтів та робити унікальні пропозиції. На основі дослідження запропоновано низку рекомендацій щодо оптимізації стратегії персональних продажів для архітектурно-будівельних компаній. На думку авторів, для досягнення високих результатів необхідно впроваджувати комплексну стратегію оптимізації персональних продажів, що включає вдосконалення комунікативних навичок, індивідуальний підхід до клієнтів, створення реальної цінності пропозицій та використання сучасних технологій.

Ключові слова: менеджер, персональний продаж, архітектурно-будівельна компанія, маркетинговий комплекс «4С», індивідуальний маркетинг, сучасні технології, стратегія персонального продажу, ефективність менеджера

Makatora D.A., Kubanov R.A., Kulikov O.P. Successful Personal Selling as an Indicator of Professional Activity Effectiveness of an Architectural and Construction Company Manager in the Context of Marketing Complex Transformation. Review article.

The research aims to study the impact of marketing complex transformation on the success of personal selling in architectural and construction companies. The concept of the '4Cs' (consumer, cost, convenience, communication) is the subject of analysis. Special attention is given to the role of personal marketing and personalised approach to customers. These are important success factors in the modern business environment. It is concluded that architectural and construction managers need to constantly improve their ability to communicate effectively, to be able to identify client needs and to make unique offers. On the basis of the study, a number of recommendations are proposed to optimise the personal selling strategy for architectural and construction companies. According to the authors, in order to achieve high results, it is necessary to implement a comprehensive strategy for the optimisation of personal selling, including the improvement of communication skills, individual approach to clients, creation of real value of offers and use of modern technologies.

Keywords: manager, personal selling, architectural and construction company, marketing complex '4Cs', individual marketing, personal selling strategy, manager's efficiency

The success of personal selling in any sphere of business is a key indicator of the efficiency of the professional activity of a manager. Due to the combination of creative and technical aspects of projects, this aspect is particularly important in the field of architecture and construction. The role of personal selling becomes even more important in the context of constant change and transformation in marketing.

The relevance of the study and the impact of marketing transformation on the process of personal selling in the architecture and construction industry will be highlighted in the following areas:

- market competition is increasing and consumer, regional and global trends are changing rapidly, creating a need for managers of architectural and construction companies to improve their personal selling skills;
- clients are becoming more demanding and informed, so managers need to be at the top of their game when it comes to communicating, demonstrating expertise and understanding client needs;
- the use of digital technologies in marketing (online advertising, social networks, virtual tours, etc.) requires managers of architecture and construction companies to adopt new approaches to personal selling;
- changes in consumer preferences and societal values affect the development of a personal selling

- strategy in the architectural and construction industry;
- changes in the legal environment and in the standards of the industry may require the managers of an architectural and construction company to actively implement new approaches and strategies in the personal selling;
 - infrastructure and urban development related to urban growth creates new opportunities and challenges for managers who must be prepared to compete and win new clients through personal selling;
 - interacting with architects, developers, investors and other key industry players requires architectural and construction company managers to be highly skilled in communicating and personal selling;
 - the need for sustainable development and energy-efficient solutions in the construction sector requires managers of architectural and construction companies to be able to effectively convince clients of the importance of these aspects during the personal selling process;
 - the globalisation of the market for construction services poses new challenges for managers, who must be prepared to carry out personalised sales with the different cultural and linguistic characteristics of the clients;
 - the production and use of innovative technologies in the construction industry means that architectural and construction managers need to be able to understand these processes in order to make a successful personal selling.

It is in this context that successful personal selling has a key role to play. The manager of an architectural and construction company needs to be a skilled communicator who is able to interact effectively with potential clients, to understand their needs and to find an individual approach to each one of them. In doing so, it is important to consider not only the standard features of a product or service, but also value to the consumer, cost to the consumer, ease of use and communicating the brand. The ability to adapt to new market realities and to offer a personalised approach to customers is therefore going to be key to succeeding in today's business environment.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Various aspects of this problem have been studied and presented in the works of Ukrainian and foreign scientists, such as F. Kotler, G. Armstrong [1], I. Artimonova [2], N. Antoshkova [3], R. Zhaldak [4], M. Druzhynin, R. Zhaldak, M. Nikolaieva [5], O. Selezneva [6], Y. Kondratiuk [7], R. Bolton, K. Lemon [8], I. Lytovchenko [9]; V. Orlova, O. Kuzmenko, O. Serhieieva [10], N. Nosan [11], S. Chernobrovkina, D. Horovyi [12], I. Budnikevych, N. Tafii [13], O. Vyaletz [14], B. Nechytailo [15], O. Hromova [16], A. Melnyk, Y. Kinash [17].

The analysis of the problem shows that the success of personal selling in architectural and construction companies is an important indicator of the effectiveness of the professional activity of a manager.

This is confirmed by the recent researches and publications of renowned Ukrainian and foreign scientists in this field. They have highlighted the importance of personal selling strategies and techniques for the successful development of the company and have studied various aspects of the problem.

When studying personal selling, it is necessary to take into account the constant changes in the global economic system and the transformation of marketing. The conditions of modern business, where it is important to be able to adapt to changes and be creative in approaches to selling products, underline the relevance of this issue. In particular, the ability to analyse the market, predict trends and adhere to the company's strategic objectives, in addition to the ability to communicate with customers, is required for successful personal selling. In the face of changes in the modern world, continuous improvement of personal selling skills will allow a manager to create competitive advantages for his company and ensure its stable development.

The aim of the article is to examine the impact of the transformation of the marketing complex on the success of personal selling in architectural and construction firms; to identify the key factors affecting the effectiveness of personal selling in a rapidly changing environment; and to develop recommendations to optimise the personal selling strategy to achieve better results in a competitive environment.

The main part

Influencing the market through marketing strategies is extremely important for any business as it is the key to the maintenance and development of its success. The traditional marketing mix of product, price, place and promotion [2] is known as the '4Ps'. These four components are considered to be the main factors influencing market demand and achieving marketing objectives.

The problem with the traditional marketing mix, however, is that it tends to focus on the needs of the seller rather than on the real needs of the consumer. This can lead to unsuccessful marketing strategies that do not consider the real needs and wants of the market [12]. In a situation such as this, it is important to rethink the traditional approach and to look for new strategies that are more effective. In this context, as suggested by Robert Waterborne, it is important to rethink the components of the marketing mix. In his view, there should be a move from the '4Ps' to the '4Cs', where the main elements will be value to the consumer, cost, convenience, communication [18]. This approach will allow us to take into account the needs of the consumer in a more accurate way and to provide them with a better service. Customer interaction can be improved and the company's competitiveness in the market increased by changing the approach from '4Ps' to '4Cs'. This approach focuses on the customer and their needs, rather than on the product and its features.

For architectural and construction companies operating in a complex and competitive industry,

Robert Waterborne's concept of moving from '4Ps' to '4Cs' is particularly relevant. An updated marketing mix for such companies may include the following components: meeting the real needs of customers (customer), minimising the total cost of building (cost), providing easy access to information about building projects (convenience), and communicating effectively with customers and building trust in the brand (communication).

By adopting a new approach, architectural and construction companies will be able to put their client needs and wishes at the forefront of their thinking, as opposed to the traditional focus on the product itself. The result will be an increase in the company's competitiveness in the marketplace and an improvement in customer satisfaction. Adherence to the 4Cs will contribute to the acquisition of new customers, the retention of existing customers and the development of stable relationships with them.

The essence of each of the stages is described in the following.

Element 1: Meeting the real needs of the customer (customer). Meeting the needs and expectations of clients is a key aspect of successful business for architectural and construction companies. Clients in the target market have high expectations in terms of quality, service and price. Therefore, successful companies need to offer not only the value of purchase, but also the value of using their services and products. The creation of value for customers contributes to an increase in customer satisfaction, an improvement in cooperation and an increase in customer loyalty [3].

Understanding and identifying the needs of their clients is the first step for architectural and construction companies. Only through the study of their requirements and expectations will the company be able to create products and services that will be of real value to the customer [4]. This approach will be the basis for an efficient use of resources and an increase in competitiveness in the market place. It is vital for the success of any architectural and construction company to increase customer loyalty and provide added value in the use of products and services. The company can enhance its reputation and ensure stable and long-term success in the construction services market by studying the needs of the target client segment and providing solutions that meet their expectations.

Element 2. Minimisation of the total cost of construction (cost). As clients are always looking for quality services and products at the best price, minimising the total cost of construction for clients of architectural and construction companies is an important aspect of business [5]. Guided by the 4Cs, in order to provide clients with maximum value and cost-effectiveness in construction projects, companies should look for ways to use resources efficiently and optimise costs.

One of the ways to minimise overall costs for clients is through the use of innovative construction technologies and methods that reduce material costs, labour costs and project delivery time [19]. Productivity can be significantly increased, energy costs reduced and the quality of work improved

through the introduction of modern technologies. Effective project management to ensure optimal resource allocation, cost control and avoidance of unnecessary expenditure is the second important aspect. Companies that focus on managing costs effectively are able to offer their customers more competitive prices while continuing to provide a high quality service. The third aspect is the identification of the right suppliers and partners for the procurement of materials and services at the best terms and conditions. It is important to establish long-term and mutually beneficial relationships with suppliers, which will help to reduce the company's costs and maintain its competitive edge. Continuously improving construction processes and finding new ways of optimising costs is the fourth aspect. Companies can work continuously to improve their performance and provide clients with the most cost-effective construction projects through the use of lean approaches and other quality and cost management methods [20]. In general, a comprehensive approach and a constant search for new ways to optimise costs and provide efficient and cost-effective solutions for their clients is required to minimise the total cost of construction for clients of architectural and construction companies.

Element 3. Easy access to construction information (convenience). For clients of architectural and construction companies, easy access to information about construction projects is an important issue [6]. Clients want to be able to get real-time information on progress, changes and other important aspects of their project. As a result, companies need to provide their clients with easy and quick access to all the relevant information about their construction projects.

Creating an online platform or application where clients can view all relevant information about their project is the first step in providing easy access to construction project information. This can include working plans, photo and video reports, working schedules and the ability to communicate with project managers and other professionals. Ensuring openness and transparency in project management is the second aspect. Clients value a sense of control and confidence that their project will be built in accordance with the plan and that the project will be a success. It is therefore important to make sure that all the information about the construction is available, that the most important points are explained and that the client is involved at every stage of the project. Using modern technology to ensure the availability of information is the third aspect. Technology can make it much easier for clients to access information about construction projects, from the introduction of remote monitoring and IoT systems to the use of cloud-based technologies for data storage and sharing. Providing clients with a personalised approach to accessing information is the fourth aspect. It is important to create a personalised approach to presenting information about a construction project that meets the client needs and expectations, as each client has unique requirements and needs. Providing opportunities for customer feedback and collaboration with the company's service department is the fifth

aspect. Customers should be able to submit questions, comments and suggestions, receive timely responses and participate in project decision-making. This will improve communication with clients and make them feel involved in the building process.

Element 4. Communicating effectively with clients and building trust and confidence in the brand (communication). A key component of success for architectural and construction companies is effective communication with clients and building trust in the brand [7]. Clients want to feel confident in the choice they are making and want to be able to obtain the necessary information [8]. Therefore, to build brand trust and provide a sense of support and understanding, it is important to ensure clear, open and effective communication with clients.

Establishing a clear plan for communicating with clients at each stage of the construction project is the first aspect in ensuring effective communication. It's important to define when and how to communicate, set expectations for sharing information and ensure there is a point of contact for the client at all times. Using different communication channels to achieve maximum audience reach is the second aspect. A variety of channels can help maintain constant contact with customers, from traditional means such as phone calls and emails to modern online platforms and social media. Proactively responding to customer questions and comments is the third aspect. Companies should be prepared to answer all questions and to take into account all the requirements of the customer. Customer satisfaction and brand trust depend on the speed and quality of responses. Ensuring clarity and openness in all communications is the fourth aspect. When dealing with a company, customers value honesty and transparency. It is important to inform the customer about all aspects of the project, including possible risks and challenges, and to develop a joint plan of action to deal with them. Maintaining relationships with clients after the project is completed is the fifth aspect. In order to build long-term relationships with clients and maintain their trust in the company's brand, it is important to provide after-sales support, answer questions and solve any problems that may arise [9].

We believe the characteristics of the concept indicate the development of personalised marketing. In order to create a deep connection between brands and consumers, personalisation in marketing is a key element. It should be noted that personalised marketing is also crucial for architectural and construction companies, as it is a key element of the customer segmentation strategy according to F. Kotler [1]. It is important not only to attract customers, but also to ensure their full satisfaction and loyalty in today's competitive environment. The goal of personalised marketing is to create a unique experience for each customer that meets their needs and desires.

The first aspect in the implementation of personalised marketing for architecture and construction companies is the systematic collection and analysis of customer data. This can include data on their previous orders, their feedback, their requirements and their preferences. The information

from these sources will help you to create a detailed profile of each client and a better understanding of their needs. Personalising goods and services is the second aspect of personalised marketing. Companies can tailor their services and projects to the specific needs of each customer based on the data collected. The result is customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. Maintaining long-term relationships with customers is the third aspect. Not only is the acquisition of a customer important, but so is the maintenance of contact with the customer after the project has been completed. This can include after-sales service, communicating on a regular basis and offering special deals to regular customers. Using technology for personalisation is the fourth aspect. To support personalised marketing, it is important to make effective use of technology, such as CRM systems. This will allow you to interact with your customers in an effective way, store important information and create personalised offers. Involving customers in the project development process is the fifth aspect. Customers can feel part of and contribute to the project by being involved in the development process. As a result, customer satisfaction increases and it is easier to build long-term customer relationships.

In summary, personalised marketing is a powerful tool for architectural and construction companies to use in building successful relationships with their clients [21]. It allows companies to respond more effectively to clients' needs and expectations, to increase satisfaction, to retain clients and to create a unique experience for each client.

The importance of personal selling as an indicator of the effectiveness of the professional activity of the manager of an architectural and construction company, which ensures the economic success of the company, is shown by the 4 C concept and the development of individual marketing. Above all, the development of individual marketing and the importance of personal sales indicate that the effectiveness of the professional activity of managers of architectural and construction companies is measured not only by sales, but also by the quality of interaction with customers, their satisfaction and loyalty. Effective interaction with clients makes it possible not only to get them to cooperate, but also to create lasting relationships which contribute to the economic success of the company.

Convincing the client to choose your company to carry out their project is the essence of personal selling in architectural and construction companies. In particular, it is about the identification of the client needs, the understanding of the client's requirements and the directing of all efforts towards the fulfilment of these needs. Through personal selling, you can get to know the client better, identify his or her wishes and avoid any possible conflicts or misunderstandings during the implementation of the project [10].

The process of personal selling involves a number of stages aimed at effective communication and mutual understanding with the customer, identification of their needs and provision of individual solutions [11].

1. Identifying and prospecting: analysing the client base to identify the most profitable customers is an

important part of the personal selling process. In this way, you can focus on the development of mutually beneficial relationships with key customers and the acquisition of similar customers.

2. Preparing to meet the client: before meeting the customer, the manager must prepare carefully by studying information about the customer's needs and wants, as well as preparing presentation materials and talking points.

3. Meeting the client: when meeting the client, it is important to create a trustworthy and professional atmosphere that will promote a positive perception of the company and its services.

4. Identifying the client needs: When communicating with the client, the manager should listen carefully and ask questions aimed at identifying the client needs and expectations. In this way you will be able to identify the best solutions that will meet the requirements of the client.

5. Presenting the product/service: in this stage, the manager presents the company's specific solutions and services, highlighting their uniqueness and how they benefit the client. It is important to point out how the services offered will meet the needs and expectations of the client.

6. Dealing with objections: if the client has doubts or objections, the manager should be prepared to discuss them and provide additional explanations to help convince the client of the benefits of working with the company.

7. Closing of the sale: after a successful presentation and resolution of all potential client questions, the manager should actively work towards the closing of the deal and determination of the optimal terms of cooperation.

8. Maintaining long-term relationships: once the deal is closed, it is important to have regular communication with the client, maintain high standards of service and be available for support and advice on future projects.

In addition to professionalism and technical training, the ability to gain the trust and understanding of the client, who relies on the manager as a specialist, is essential to overall success in personal selling.

The ability to listen and feel the customer is a key component of effective personal selling. This means being proactive in identifying their needs, having the ability to empathise with them and being prepared to respond quickly to their changing needs. It is also important to identify opportunities to add value or improve the project, which further enhances the value offered to the customer. Developing individual personal selling strategies for managers is very important in our view.

An individual personal selling strategy for a manager in an architectural and construction company is a unique approach to each client, with the aim of gaining their co-operation and meeting their needs. This means that, in order to achieve the most successful results, the sales strategy must be adapted to the personal needs, preferences and goals of each client.

Elements of individual personal selling strategies can include analysis of customer needs, personal

contact, development of individual offers and the use of technology to effectively engage customers. Monitoring and analysing performance and providing post-sales support are also important.

Here's a closer look at the elements of a personal selling strategy.

Carrying out a customer needs analysis is important because it allows you to understand the factors that are important to the customer when it comes to choosing a housing or building solution [13]. For example, if the client has a preference for environmentally friendly materials and energy-efficient technologies, the manager can offer projects or solutions that meet these criteria. This analysis is the basis for the development of the best solution for the customer, in line with his or her needs and expectations. A family looking for a home in a child-friendly location close to schools, kindergartens and entertainment facilities is another practical example. In this case, the manager can offer properties that are in line with these requirements and provide a comfortable environment for the children's development. In addition, budget, design and style preferences and other individual factors may be taken into account when analysing the client needs. For example, the manager can offer budget options that meet the customer's financial capabilities or consider financing options if the customer has a limited budget. In this way, the analysis of client needs not only makes it possible to identify the key requirements and priorities of the customer, but also to offer individual solutions that meet the unique needs of each customer. The result is the development of long-term relationships with clients, the fulfilment of their needs and the achievement of successful transactions in the architecture and construction business.

Indeed, a key element of successful cooperation in the architecture and construction business is the establishment of a personal relationship with the client. A pleasant and friendly interaction makes it possible to build up trust and a sense of comfort between the manager and the client, which contributes to the successful completion of the transaction [14]. For example, the manager can identify common interests or values that will help to build an even stronger relationship with the client by responding to the client's individual needs and wishes. This could be a shared interest in design, architecture or construction, or a shared understanding of certain aspects of the project. Establishing a personal connection can also form the basis of a long-term relationship. The client may choose the company for further projects or recommend it to friends if the manager shows interest and attention to the client, builds trust and mutual understanding. A practical example of this is when a manager shows an interest in the personal needs and wishes of the client, as well as in their common interests. For example, they can talk about common hobbies or interests, which will help to build an even closer relationship and will create positive emotions in the client. Building trust, understanding and a fruitful relationship in the future is an important stage of the interaction.

The offer of individual solutions for the client is an important step in the interaction between the manager of an architectural and construction company and the client. The client's interest can be stimulated and the offer made more attractive by highlighting the benefits of a particular project or the possibilities for design refinement [15]. For example, the manager can offer ways to refine the design or plan to meet the client needs and desires if the client has expressed a desire to own an existing project. This will allow the client to see how the project can be adapted to meet his or her needs and requirements, which will create a more personalised approach and increase the likelihood of a successful transaction. Furthermore, explaining all aspects of the proposal to the client and giving them the opportunity to ask questions is important.

The customer is more likely to make an informed choice and accept the offer the more detailed and clear the information provided. An example of a practical application of this is when a manager of an architectural and construction company offers a client an individual solution for the design of a house that suits his or her style and needs. The manager can gain the client's attention and reach a joint decision by showing the benefits of this proposal and the possibilities for improvement. Thus, an important stage in the interaction that contributes to a successful transaction and customer satisfaction is to provide the customer with individualised offers that take into account their needs and wishes.

In the interaction with a customer, a manager should make use of modern technologies in order to effectively attract customers. There is no doubt that with the use of modern technologies a manager can significantly improve the interaction with the customer and make the process of co-operation more efficient [16]. For example, customers can better imagine their future home and make an informed choice through the use of virtual tours or mock-ups. This approach allows the client to see the design solutions, the layout and the architectural features of the project in the most realistic way possible. For example, a manager of an architectural company can do virtual tours of a building project with the help of software. This greatly simplifies the selection and decision-making process by allowing the client to walk through the house or apartment online, feel the space and evaluate the design. In order to be available to clients at any time and at any stage of the transaction, it is also important to be able to work effectively with online communications. For example, you can easily and quickly exchange information and documents and respond to clients' questions in real time by using chat platforms, video conferencing or e-mail. An example of the practical use of technology is when a manager of an architectural company offers a client a virtual tour of a house or apartment project, showing all the benefits and features of the project. As a result, the client has a better understanding of the scope of the project and an improvement in the quality of information perception. In this way, the use of modern technologies allows the managers of architectural and construction companies to improve the cooperation

with the clients and to make the process of interaction more efficient and more comfortable for all parties.

Post-trade customer support may be the final stage of an individual strategy. A manager can monitor the quality of order execution, provide advice and make recommendations for future improvements [17], and perform a number of other functions to support the customer after the transaction. In theory, this helps to retain customers and ensure continued positive relationships. Customers feel that their needs and satisfaction are a top priority for the company, which contributes to their loyalty and recommendation of the organisation to others. A practical example of post-transaction customer care could be: upon completion of a housing project, a manager can contact the customer to ensure that everything is in line with their expectations and quality standards. In addition, he or she can offer advice on the operation of the building, practical maintenance tips and solutions to any problems that may arise. In addition, the manager can regularly send information about new technologies or services that can improve the client's life, or recommend specialists to solve various problems. In this way, post-transaction customer care is an important stage in a manager's strategy, which makes it possible to maintain long-term relationships with customers and ensure their satisfaction and loyalty to the company.

In order to optimise the personal sales strategy of architectural and construction companies, we offer the following recommendations based on the study:

1. Continuous improvement of skills in effective communication with clients:
 - develop the ability to listen, empathise and understand the client needs;
 - improve presenting and persuading techniques;
 - become acquainted with the technologies used in personal selling (CRM systems, virtual reality, etc.).
2. Implementation of an individual approach to each customer:
 - carry out a detailed analysis of the needs, requirements and expectations of each individual customer;
 - develop unique propositions that best meet the needs of a particular client;
 - provide, at all stages of the relationship, personalised customer support.
3. Increase emphasis on customer value creation:
 - focus not only on the features of the product or service, but also on the practical benefits it brings to the customer;
 - provide the customer with additional services and advice that increase the value of the offer;
 - offer flexibility in choosing solutions to suit their budget and preferences.
4. The use of modern technologies for the optimisation of the personal sales process:
 - implement CRM systems for effective customer relationship management;
 - use virtual reality and 3D modelling tools to present projects visually;

— actively use online channels to communicate and interact with customers in real time.

5. Post-sale support and maintenance of customers: monitoring of customer satisfaction and prompt response:

— monitor and respond promptly to customer needs as they arise;

— provide equipment operation advice and recommendations;

— keep the client informed of new products, services and opportunities for collaboration.

By implementing these recommendations, architectural and construction companies can optimise their personal selling strategy, increase client interaction efficiency and achieve better competitive results.

Conclusion

The success of personal selling in architectural and construction companies is a key indicator of the professional performance of a manager. The role of personal selling is becoming increasingly important in the context of constant change and transformation in marketing. In order to adapt to the new market realities, managers in architectural and construction companies need to improve their personal selling skills.

The '4Cs' concept (consumer, cost, convenience, communication) is important for architectural and construction companies as it allows them to rethink the traditional marketing approach and focus on customer needs and requirements. The application of the 4Cs will be a boost to the company's competitiveness and customer satisfaction.

Personalised marketing and a personalised approach to customers are key success factors in today's business environment. Managers of architectural and construction companies must constantly improve their skills in effective communication, the identification of client needs and the provision of unique offerings.

Using modern technologies such as CRM systems, virtual reality and online communication allows you to optimise the personal selling process, increase the efficiency of interacting with clients and ensure the company's competitive advantage.

Architectural and construction companies need to implement a comprehensive personal selling strategy that includes improved communication skills, a personalised approach to clients, adding real value to clients and projects, and the use of modern technology in order to achieve high results in a competitive environment. This approach will ensure the company's stable development and strengthen its market position.

Abstract

Introduction. The article deals with the issue of successful personal selling as an indicator of professional activity effectiveness of an architectural and construction company manager in the context of marketing complex transformation. The relevance of the topic is due to the constant changes in the global economy and marketing, which require managers to improve their personal selling skills in order to ensure the competitiveness of the company.

The purpose of the study is to examine the impact of the transformation of the marketing complex on the success of personal selling in architectural and construction companies; to identify the key factors that influence the effectiveness of personal selling; to develop recommendations for the optimisation of the personal selling strategy.

Research methods. This article uses analytical, synthesising, generalising and comparative methods to study theoretical and practical aspects of personal selling in architecture and construction.

Results of the study. The concept of the '4Cs' is analysed as an alternative to the traditional marketing complex of the '4Ps', which allows for a better consideration of the needs of the consumer. The key elements of the new marketing complex for architecture and construction companies are identified and justified: value for the customer, total cost for the customer, product availability, effective communication with customers. The importance of individual marketing and a personalised approach to the client for a successful personal selling strategy is considered. The elements of an individual personal selling strategy are proposed: analysis of the customer's needs, establishment of a personal relationship, provision of individual solutions, use of modern technologies, after-sales service.

Conclusions. The success of the personal selling is a key indicator of the effectiveness of the professional activity of the manager of an architectural and construction company. In order to achieve high results, it is necessary to implement a comprehensive strategy for the optimisation of personal selling, including the improvement of communication skills, an individual approach to clients, the creation of real value in offers and the use of modern technologies. This approach will be a guarantee of the company's stable development and the strengthening of its market position.

Based on the study, the author offers a number of recommendations for optimising the personal selling strategy for architectural and construction companies, in particular: continuously improve effective communication skills with clients, introduce an individual approach to each client, strengthen the focus of the individual offer on creating value for the client, use modern technologies to optimise the personal selling process, and ensure continuous support and maintenance of clients after the transaction is completed. Implementing these recommendations will enable architectural and construction companies to optimise their personal selling strategy, increase the efficiency of interacting with clients and achieve better results in a competitive environment.

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